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The EU's Role – Globally, Multilaterally, Internally – as a Human Rights Actor (in the Face of State HRJ Practices)

1. Three layers of EU human rights enforcement

This report explores the role of the EU as a human rights promoter, including its ability to monitor and control the legitimacy of the use of human rights justifications by state actors. Broadly, the EU's activities in human rights governance can be described in three layers. First and most obviously, the EU is able to act vis-à-vis its Member State as a supranational power. This role includes the issuing of legislation and other regulatory acts aimed at ensuring the enforcement of fundamental rights in and through national law, but also the executive and judicial control, through the Commission and the EU Court of Justice (CJEU), of the Member States' compliance with Union law, most importantly with the Charter of Fundamental Rights (CFR). Second, the EU acts on the international scene as a subject of international law through agreement with (mostly) states outside the Union. These agreements may have as an objective or a condition to ensure the enforcement of human rights, and they are also subject to the scrutiny of the CJEU to ensure that the international agreements themselves are compatible with primary EU law including the CFR. Third, a growing literature has observed that the EU also acts as a global or extraterritorial actor, exercising power over third countries through the extraterritorial reach of its internal, unilateral legal measures – often itself using human rights justifications to legitimise its influence. These three roles will be examined in the following.

2. The EU as a Supranational Actor

In the relationship between the EU and its Member States, the latter may invoke human rights as a justification for deviations from Union law requirements. As a point of departure, human rights – at least, human rights as protected in the national laws of the Member States – do not

constitute ‘trumps’ in the EU legal order; instead, following the doctrine of supremacy, the trump function is assigned to any provision of EU law in relation to one of national law, meaning that the EU’s conception of fundamental rights prevail over that of the Member States or one/some of them.¹ This idea has been questioned in more recent literature, with commentators arguing that the need to protect the process of integration which underpins the principle of supremacy no longer – given the increased stability of the Union resulting from the level of integration achieved since its establishment – justifies absolut supremacy overriding even Member State constitutional rights.² It has also been at least to some extent challenged by the introduction, through the Treaty of Lisbon, of the Union obligation to respect the Member States’ national constitutional identity, which arguably may include at least parts of their fundamental rights protection; however, the CJEU has been reluctant to allow national fundamental rights protection to prevail as an expression of constitutional identity.³

In the CJEU’s case law, C-399/11 *Melloni* remains the landmark ruling.⁴ In that case, an individual had been convicted *in absentia* by Italian courts to ten years imprisonment on bankruptcy fraud charges. Following his arrest in another Member State, Spain, on the basis of an European arrest warrant (EAW), the question arose as to whether the *in absentia* conviction was compatible with the fundamental right to a fair hearing. While the CJEU, on a reference from the Spanish Constitutional Court, held that the Italian conviction was compatible with Articles 47 and 48 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (CFR), the national court argued that the Spanish constitution provided a higher level of protection for fair trial rights, which precluded litigation *in absentia* for serious crimes. As Article 53 CFR provides that the Charter cannot have as effect to lessen the human rights protection provided by national constitutions, the Spanish court argued that the national constitutional right to a fair trial should take precedence over the secondary legislation demanding Mr Melloni’s extradition to Italy, namely the EAW Framework Decision. The CJEU rejected that interpretation. Citing its 1970 *Internationale Handelsgesellschaft* ruling on the primacy of EU law, it held that national fundamental rights standards may be applied only if they uphold (or surpass) the minimum level of protection provided by the Charter and *if ‘the primacy, unity and effectiveness of EU law are not thereby compromised’*.⁵

Melloni was followed by *MAS*, in which the Italian Constitutional Court questioned the CJEU’s ruling in a prior preliminary reference case (*Taricco*).⁶ In *Taricco*, the Court had ruled that national courts were obliged to set aside national rules on limitation periods for the prosecution of tax offences, in order to ensure the effective enforcement of European VAT law. In *MAS*, the referring court pointed out that this would be contrary to the constitutional prohibition of retroactivity in criminal law. The CJEU accepted this objection, ruling that national courts are not obliged or indeed, not allowed, to follow *Taricco* if this would lead to an infringement of the principle of *nullum crimen sine lege praevia*. While it is not clear from the Court’s reasoning in *MAS*

¹ Cf Fabbrini, *Fundamental Rights in Europe: Challenges and Transformations in Comparative Perspective*, OUP 2014, 9; Besselink,

² Lindeboom, Why EU Law Claims Supremacy, *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies*, Vol. 38, No. 2 (2018), pp. 328–356, 334; Cf also Letsas, Harmonic Law: The Case Against Pluralism, in Dickson and Eleftheriades, *The Philosophical Foundations of EU Law*, OUP 2012, 77–108 at 101, who makes a similar argument from on more ethically informed grounds.

³ See de Visser, Dealing with Divergencies in Fundamental Rights Standards: Case C-399/11 *Stefano Melloni v. Ministerio Fiscal*, Judgement (Grand Chamber) of 26 February 2013, Not Yet Reported, 20 MJECL (2013) 576–588 at 583; Claes, National Identity and the Protection of Fundamental Rights, 27 *European Public Law*, (2021), 517–536.

⁴ Case C-399/11 *Stefano Melloni v Ministerio Fiscal*, ECLI:EU:C:2013:107.

⁵ *Id.*, paras 59–60. Emphasis added.

⁶ Case C-42/17 *M.A.S. and M.B.*, ECLI:EU:C:2017:936; Case C-105/14, *Criminal proceedings against Taricco and others*, ECLI:EU:C:2015:555.

whether the limitation on the effectiveness of EU secondary law followed from the *national* principle of non-retroactivity or from (an upgraded version of) the similar or identical principle enshrined in Article 49 CFR and other sources of European law,⁷ the Court has subsequently clarified the former to be the case.⁸ Thus, *M.A.S.* confirms the principle laid down in *Melloni*, but differs in its application.

The standard that Member State human rights justifications are subjected to under the *Melloni* test remain underdeveloped. Two vague criteria can however be identified in case law. First, the crucial difference between *Melloni* and *M.A.S.* appears to have been that the level of harmonisation in the field. While, arguably, in both cases the relevant secondary act left some relevant procedural matters to be regulated by national law, the Court of Justice in *Melloni* specifically pointed out that the question was resolved by Article 4a of the EAW Framework Decision, whereas in *M.A.S.* it instead emphasised the rules on time-barring had not been harmonised at the relevant time.⁹ In subsequent case law, the presence of a ‘a situation where action of the Member States is not entirely determined by EU law’ appears to have been elevated to a precondition for the applicability of Article 53 CFR.¹⁰ This would entail that, that where a situation is fully harmonised, primacy is absolute regardless of the standard of protection offered by national constitutions. It remains unclear whether and how, in situations only *partially* determined by EU law, the level of harmonisation can factor in the balance of interests between the national constitutional norm and the effectiveness of EU law.¹¹

Second, in *Euro Box Promotion* the Court summarily rejected the suggestion of upholding a (potentially) higher national fundamental rights standard with reference to its giving rise to a *systemic risk* of non-enforcement of EU law.¹² It did not, however, elaborate on this. In the subsequent *Lin* judgment, the Court at the same time accepted one deviation from Union requirements on the basis of national fundamental rights standards going beyond those of the CFR, ‘*notwithstanding* the existence of a systemic risk of serious fraud offences affecting the financial interests of the European Union going unpunished’, and rejected another as ‘liable to exacerbate the systemic risk that serious fraud affecting the financial interests of the European Union will escape any criminal penalty’.¹³ Thus, the existence of a systemic risk of non-enforcement is not in itself sufficient to override a national human rights justification, but it remains unclear under what circumstances a risk is big enough or its effects significant enough to have that effect.¹⁴

In sum, the judicial control of Member State human rights justifications within the scope of EU law remains underdeveloped. Generally, however, the *Melloni* test is perceived as strict, with *M.A.S.* and, to some extent, *Lin* being the only examples so far of successfully defending

⁷ Cf C-42/17 *M.A.S.*, paras 52–53.

⁸ See Case C-107/23 PPU [*Lin*], ECLI:EU:C:2023:606, para. 116; AG Sánchez-Bordona in the same case, ECLI:EU:C:2023:532, para. 141; and further Rauegger, National constitutional rights and the primacy of EU law: *M.A.S.* Case C-42/17, *M.A.S. and M.B.*, Judgment of the Court of Justice (Grand Chamber) of 5 December 2017, EU:C:2017:936, 55 CMLRev (2018) 1521–1548, 1532.

⁹ C-399/11 *Melloni*, paras 61–62; C-42/17 *M.A.S.* paras 44–45. See also Rauegger, op. cit. at 1532.

¹⁰ See Case C-476/17 *Pelham GmbH and Others v Ralf Hütter and Florian Schneider-Esleben*, ECLI:EU:C:2019:624, para. 80; Case C-357/19 *Criminal proceedings against PM and Others (Euro Box Promotion)*, ECLI:EU:C:2021:1034, para. 211; C-107/23 PPU [*Lin*] para. 110.

¹¹ Cf Opinion of AG Bobek in C-310/16 *Criminal proceedings against Petar Dživev and others*, ECLI:EU:C:2018:623, paras 92–94; and further Bonelli, Growing pains: Direct effect, primacy and fundamental rights after *Lin* Case C-107/23 PPU, *Lin*, Judgment of the Court (Grand Chamber) of 24 July 2023, EU:C:2023:606, 61 CMLRev (2024) 1045–1076 at 1073f.

¹² C-357/19 *Euro Box Promotions*, para. 212.

¹³ C-107/23 PPU *Lin*, paras 118 and 121, respectively (emphasis added).

¹⁴ Similarly Bonelli, op. cit. 1072.

national fundamental rights standards over the primacy and effectiveness of Union law.¹⁵ The legitimacy of the Court's position has been questioned, with the relevance of both the harmonization criterion¹⁶ and the systemic risk criterion¹⁷ being questioned and the Court's relative openness to fundamental rights protection in *M.A.S.* described as a surprising exception motivated by strategic considerations rather than legal argumentation.¹⁸ Overall, the problem appears to be one of output legitimacy; the Court's position prioritises the uniformity and effectiveness of Union law in non-fundamental matters over the protection of fundamental rights arguments. As one commentator has pointed out, the issue is ultimately political, and should be resolved by democratic, rather than purely judicial, dialogue.¹⁹

3. *The EU as an International Actor*

On the international arena, the EU encounters states in a position of formal equality between independent subjects of international law.²⁰ Respect for human rights is a core objective of EU external relations and the Union regularly proclaims its ambition to be a leading actor in the promotion of human rights worldwide.²¹ However, the political willingness to pursue this goal and the level of consensus between the Member States has been questioned, with the Union being regularly accused of operating a double standard subjecting external partners to higher fundamental rights standards than it enforces internally and avoiding placing itself under effective scrutiny.²²

The EU's own actions on the international arena is subject to judicial control by the Court of Justice under the procedure prescribed by Article 218(11) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU), according to which a Member State or core EU institution (Commission, Council, Parliament) may request the CJEU's opinion as to an envisaged international agreement's compatibility with EU primary law. The Court's opinion is binding in the sense that a negative opinion precludes the entry into force of the agreement until the conflict is resolved. One of the most controversial opinions delivered through this procedure concerned the Union's proposed accession to the European Convention of Human Rights (ECHR), which is prescribed in the Treaties and would have placed the Union under the jurisdiction of the European Court of Human Rights. However, in Opinion 2/13, the Court held that the proposed accession agreement was contrary to EU law in several respects, most of them connected in various ways to the autonomy of the EU legal order and the position of the CJEU itself as the final arbiter of all matters EU law.²³

¹⁵ See Millet, "Why Article 53 of the Charter should ground the application of national fundamental rights in fully harmonised areas" in Bobek and Adams-Prassl (eds), *The EU Charter of Fundamental Rights in the Member States* (Hart Publishing, 2020), 441–464.

¹⁶ Millet, *op. cit.* 459f; for opposing opinion see Bonelli, *op. cit.* 1074.

¹⁷ Cf Opinion of AG Sánchez-Bordona in C-107/23 PPU, *Lin*, para. 145.

¹⁸ Besselink and Bonelli, Back and Forth Between Sovereignty and Constitutionalism: The Court of Justice's Constitutional Case Law. 14 *European Constitutional Law Review* (2018), 665–674.

¹⁹ De Boer, Case C-399/11, *Stefano Melloni v Ministero Fiscal*, Judgment of the Court (Grand Chamber) of 26 February 2013, nyr. Addressing rights divergences under the Charter, 30 *CMLRev* (2013) 1083–1104.

²⁰ This report will not specifically examine the relationship between the EU and its Member States on the international arena and thus does not address the question of mixed agreements.

²¹ See Article 21 of the Treaty on the European Union; further Wessel and Larik, *EU External Relations Law: Text, Cases and Materials*, Bloomsbury 2020, 327ff.; and critically Leino, The Journey Towards All that is Good and Beautiful: Human Rights and 'Common Values' as Guiding Principles of EU Foreign Relations Law, in Cremona and de Witte (eds), *EU Foreign Relations Law: Constitutional Fundamentals* (Hart 2008) 259–289.

²² See eg. de Búrca, The Road Not Taken: The European Union as a Global Human Rights Actor, 105 *American Journal of International Law* (2011) 649–693.

²³ For more detailed discussion, see eg Halberstam, "It's the Autonomy, Stupid!" A Modest Defense of Opinion 2/13 on EU Accession to the ECHR, and the Way Forward, 16 *German Law Journal* (2015) 105–146; Krenn, Autonomy and effectiveness as common concerns: a path to ECHR accession after Opinion 2/13 16 *German Law*

The Opinion is relevant for the present purposes for two reasons. First, it constitutes a perpetuation of the prioritisation of the autonomy – which is largely a corollary to the primacy – of EU law over the promotion of fundamental rights.²⁴ Second, it contributes to the perception of a double standard or even an European exceptionalism,²⁵ as the CJEU ‘seemingly lives and breathes the idea that the EU should be given special treatment by virtue of its specific characteristics’, with the result that it cannot be made subject to the scrutiny its Member States as well as many other states in the region already faces.²⁶ At the same time, the CJEU has held in its landmark *Kadi* ruling that as international legal acts enter into the EU legal order (as an effect of the EU’s participation in international organisations), the Court has competence to review the compatibility of such acts with the EU’s own foundational values including its fundamental rights regime.²⁷

However, while these observations are intimately related to the Union’s internal fundamental rights review examined above, as well as to the global reach of EU law to be examined below, they do not directly bear on the EU’s role in relation to human rights justifications offered by other Member States. EU law appears to have little to offer in this regard. If the justifications are offered in international non-contractual relations (for instance, in Russia’s invasion of Ukraine) or in pre-contractual negotiations, the appropriate reactions appear to belong to the political rather than legal sphere, whereas if they are provided in defense of another state party’s deviation from an international treaty, that would presumably be settled by the designated dispute resolution mechanism for that treaty (which, however, pursuant to Article 272 TFEU may be arbitration proceedings before the CJEU). It is thus only rather exceptionally that a third state’s actions as an international legal subject would become a matter of Union law.

4. The EU as a Global Actor

A third facet of the EU’s role, or potential, as a human rights actor stems from the so-called *Brussels effect*:²⁸ the Union’s use of market forces to exercise unilateral regulatory powers on a global scale. The basic principle is that standards put in place for the EU internal markets must be complied with not only by EU actors, but also by any external actor wishing to operate on the Union market.²⁹ If the costs of operating dual standards is too high, such extra-EU traders may opt for following EU standards across their whole operation. Because of its reliance on market forces, however, this practice is most effective on economical issues or issues that directly impacts economical activities, such as environmental protection measures, food and product safety, or the handling of personal data. For other, non-market issues, including core human rights, the EU’s unilateral regulatory power is considerably lesser on the global stage.³⁰

Naturally, there has been attempts at push-back against the extra-territorial reach of Union internal legal measures, including on fundamental rights grounds. One well-known example is

Journal (2015) 147-167; Spaventa, A very fearful court? The protection of fundamental rights in the European Union after opinion 2/13, 22 *Maastricht journal of European and comparative law* (2015) 35-56.

²⁴ Besselink and Bonelli, op. cit. 669f.

²⁵ Cf Ličková, European Exceptionalism in International Law, 19 *The European Journal of International Law* (2008) 463–490, especially a propos the so-called *Bosphorus* presumption according to which EU law enjoys a presumption of compatibility with the ECHR.

²⁶ Lindeboom, Why EU Law Claims Supremacy, 38 *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies* (2018) 328–356, 256.

²⁷ Joined cases C-402/05 P and C-415/05 P, *Yassin Abdullah Kadi and Al Barakaat International Foundation*, ECLI:EU:C:2008:461, and further de Búrca, *The European Court of Justice and the International Legal Order after Kadi*, 51 *Harvard International Law Journal* (2010) 1-49.

²⁸ Bradford, *The Brussels Effect: How the European Union Rules the World* (OUP 2020).

²⁹ For an elaboration, see Bradford, op. cit. 26ff.

³⁰ Bradford, op. cit. 89.

the *Inuit* cases, pursued both before the CJEU and within the World Trade Organisation (WTO) dispute resolution system and concerning the prohibition on the sale and marketing of seal products on the EU market. The cases are illustrative of the hurdles facing an extra-EU actor seeking to challenge Union measures and will be examined in some detail.

Before the CJEU, actions were brought by representatives for the indigenous populations in Norway, Canada and Greenland. A first case was, unsurprisingly, rejected as inadmissible on the basis of the Court's long-standing and infamously restrictive interpretation of the standing requirements for so-called non-privileged applicants under Article 263(4) TFEU.³¹ It is worth observing that the same *locus standi* criteria will apply for a third state seeking to challenge an EU legal measure before the CJEU,³² meaning that such challenges will be admissible only under rather narrowly defined circumstances that singles out the state in question as both directly and individually – which more or less translates to ‘uniquely’³³ – affected by the legal act in question.³⁴ Unlike private entities, state actors will also not, or only in exceptional circumstances, be able to obtain indirect access to the CJEU through national courts and the preliminary reference procedure.³⁵

A subsequent case brought by largely the same applicants alleging that the regulation in question infringed upon their fundamental rights, including most notably the right to property, was rejected in substance (following a procedural peculiarity whereby the General Court decided to rule on the case in substance without a prior examination of its admissibility;³⁶ had this course not been taken, it is likely that the action had again been dismissed for lack of standing).³⁷ This demonstrates that, once an action has moved passed the admissibility hurdle, the CJEU is competent to review the effects of EU unilateral measures on the fundamental rights enjoyed by third country nationals dwelling outside of the Union territory.³⁸ Such actions may be based on the CFR, which has been considered to apply to EU action without territorial limitations,³⁹ but can likely also be based on more general human rights argumentation.⁴⁰

At the same time, Norway and Canada brought actions against the EU before the WTO Dispute Settlement Body (DSB). While the EU seal products regime's compatibility with fundamental rights, including the rights of indigenous peoples, have been questioned,⁴¹ the WTO setting is

³¹ Case C-583/11 P, *Inuit Tapiriit Kanatami v Parliament and Council*, ECLI:EU:C:2013:625. For a discussion of this case law in particular in environmental matters, see Hadjiyianni, *Judicial protection and the environment in the EU legal order: missing pieces for a complete puzzle of legal remedies*, 58 *Common Market Law Review* (2021) 777–812, 781ff.

³² Case C-872/19 P *Venezuela v Council*, ECLI:EU:C:2021:507, paras 41–53.

³³ Winter, *Plaumann Withering: Standing before the EU General Court Underway from Distinctive to Substantial Concern*, 15 *European Journal of Legal Studies* (2023) 85–124.

³⁴ In the above-mentioned C-872/19 P *Venezuela v Council* case, the contested Regulation (Council Regulation (EU) 2017/2063 of 13 November 2017 concerning restrictive measures in view of the situation in Venezuela) singled out Venezuela in its title and first two recitals; yet, the General Court did not find the state to be ‘explicitly and specifically referred to in the contested provisions’ in a way to make it directly affected (Case T-65/18 *Venezuela v Council*, ECLI:EU:T:2019:6499, and its action was held admissible only following appeal).

³⁵ See Hadjiyianni, *The EU as a Global Regulator for Environmental Protection* (Hart 2019) 149.

³⁶ Case T-526/10, *Inuit Tapiriit Kanatami v Parliament and Council*, ECLI:EU:T:2013:215, paras 20–21.

³⁷ Case C-398/13 P *Inuit Tapiriit Kanatami v Parliament and Council*, ECLI:EU:C:2015:535.

³⁸ Cf also the above-mentioned joined cases C-402/05 P and C-415/05 P *Kadi and Al Barakaat*, in which one of the applicants was a third country national resident in Saudi Arabia.

³⁹ Moreno-Lax and Costello, *The Extraterritorial Application of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights: From Territoriality to Facticity, the Effectiveness Model*, in Peers et al (eds), *Commentary on the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights* (Hart 2014) 1657–1683.

⁴⁰ For an extensive discussion, see Hadjiyianni, *op. cit.* 190ff.

⁴¹ See eg Cambou, *The Impact of the Ban on Seal Products on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples: A European Issue*, 5 *Yearbook of Polar Law* (2013) 389–415.

strictly limited to technical trade law issues, making the forum unsuitable for the (explicit) adjudication of human rights concerns.⁴² Although striking down the EU measures for discriminating against Canadian seal products compared to Greenlandic ones, the WTO Appellate Body concluded that the EU regime was in principle justifiable on the public moral grounds of animal welfare.⁴³ Opening up for a broad construction of the public morals exception, the position may easily be expanded to include human rights concerns.⁴⁴ Interestingly, this implies that the defendant before the WTO DSB – i.e., in the case of EU internal measures with extraterritorial effects, the EU itself – is able to rely on human rights as a justification, whereas the applicant third states affected by the measures are not.

The legitimacy of EU unilateral action with extraterritorial effects is debated. Focusing in particular on the environmental field, Hadjiyianni observes that EU measures with extraterritorial effects face three ‘legitimacy gaps’. These are connected, first, to accountability, considering the lack of relationship, such as for instance democratic elections, between those enacting the norms and those bound by them; second, to participation and representation (input legitimacy), as those affected by the rules do not have a voice in their creation; and third, to justice (output legitimacy), which is largely an outpouring of the first two as the absence of effective participation and accountability routes increases the risk that the measures adopted fail to fairly consider the interests of third countries and their nationals.⁴⁵ Similar concerns are raised – and largely brushed aside – by Bradford under the labels of ‘regulatory protectionism’, concerning the risk that EU measures, rather than serving the ideals they claim to promote, function as protection for European commercial interests, and ‘regulatory imperialism’, understood in the best case as undermining democratic accountability and third country political processes and in the worst as seeking global domination.⁴⁶ Her defense, which argues in the first respect that no protectionist effects have been empirically established and in the second that the EU is mostly benevolent and at any rate a more competent and/or democratic regulator than many other states, is not entirely convincing.⁴⁷

In sum, while the EU can and to some extent does rely on the global reach of EU law to for the global promotion of Union values, including fundamental rights, this practice gives rise to concerns as regards the ability of third states to make their own perceptions of human rights heard.⁴⁸ These concerns pertain both to the adoption of EU measures, in which third state actors have no position, and the ex post challenge of such measures, where access to the CJEU is heavily curtailed by the restrictive standing regime.

⁴² Beqiraj, *The Delicate Equilibrium of EU Trade Measures: The Seals Case*, 14 *German Law Journal* (2015) 279–319, 300f.

⁴³ WTO Appellate Body Report, *European Communities—Measures prohibiting the importation and marketing of seal products*. WT/DS400/AB/R, WT/DS401/AB/R.

⁴⁴ Shaffer and Pabian, *World Trade Organization-Agreement on Technical Barriers to Trade-General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade-discrimination-protection of public morals regarding animal welfare-indigenous communities* 109 *American Journal of International Law* (2015) 154–161, 158.

⁴⁵ Hadjiyianni, *op. cit.* 50ff.

⁴⁶ Bradford, *op. cit.* 235ff.

⁴⁷ Cf Hadjiyianni, *The European Union as a Global Regulatory Power*, 41 *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies* (2021) 243–264; Lindseth, *The Brussels Effect: How the European Union Rules the World*, 70 *American Journal of Comparative Law* (2022) 641–645, 642, who accuses Bradford of ‘downplaying broadly recognized democratic, geopolitical, and macroeconomic limitations.’

⁴⁸ On the illusion of universality of human rights, see Leino, *op. cit.* 263.